
Research Article

***Ophrys* × *italica*, a replacement name for *Ophrys* × *varvarae* D'Alonzo (Orchidaceae)**

Rajeev Kumar Singh and Vineet Kumar Rawat*

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AllMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

*E-mail: rawat_vk2107@rediffmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6828-5108>

Article Details: Received: 2025-11-15 | Accepted: 2026-01-26 | Available online: 2026-01-28

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: A new name, *Ophrys* × *italica* R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, is proposed here to replace the illegitimate name *O.* × *varvarae* D'Alonzo, which is a later homonym of *O.* × *varvarae* Faller & Kreutz (Orchidaceae). In addition, a new combination and status is proposed here for *Ophrys* × *marmarensis* nothosubsp. *saskiana* Lappler as *O.* × *saskiana* (Lappler) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat

Keywords: East Aegean Islands, Italy, *Ophrys bertolonii*, *Ophrys fusca*, *Ophrys* × *marmarensis* nothosubsp. *saskiana*

Introduction

The genus *Ophrys* L. comprises about 80 naturally occurring species and more than 400 hybrid taxa, distributed from Macaronesia and Europe to the Caucasus, and from the Mediterranean region eastwards to Turkmenistan (Hennecke, 2021). The nothospecies name *Ophrys* × *varvarae* D'Alonzo (GIROS Orch. Spont. Eur. 67: 150. 2024) is illegitimate because it is a later homonym of *O.* × *varvarae* Faller & Kreutz (Mitteilungsbl. Arbeitskreis Heimische Orchid. Baden-Wurtemberg 22: 363. 1990), in accordance with Article 53.1 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025). Therefore, the replacement name *O.* × *italica* R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat is proposed here. Additionally, a new combination and status are proposed for *O.* × *marmarensis* nothosubsp. *saskiana* Lappler, which is raised to nothospecific rank as *O.* × *saskiana* (Lappler) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat.

Nomenclature

Ophrys × *italica* R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Ophrys* × *varvarae* D'Alonzo, GIROS Orch. Spont. Eur. 67(2): 150. 2024, *nom. illeg., non* Faller & Kreutz, Mitteilungsbl. Arbeitskreis Heimische Orchid. Baden-Württemberg 22(2): 363. 1990.

Holotype: Italy, Apulia, Murgia Bari, Pulicchio di Gravina in Puglia, 480 m, 6 August 2024, *F. D'Alonzo* 59078 (BI).

Distribution: Italy.

Hybrid parents: *Ophrys bertolonii* Moretti × *Ophrys lupercalis* Devillers-Tersch. & Devillers (≡ *Ophrys fusca* Link subsp. *fusca*).

Ophrys* × *saskiana (Läpple) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *comb. et stat. nov.*

≡ *Ophrys* × *marmarensis* nothosubsp. *saskiana* Läpple, Mitteilungsbl. Arbeitskreis Heimische Orchid. Baden-Württemberg 24(4): 627. 1992.

Distribution: East Aegean Islands.

Hybrid parents: *Ophrys holosericea* (Burm.f.) Greuter subsp. *holosericea* × *Ophrys umbilicata* Desf. subsp. *rhodia* H.Baumann & Künkele [= *Ophrys rhodia* (H.Baumann & Künkele) P.Delforge].

Acknowledgements

The author are thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities.

References

- Hennecke, M. (2021). The genus *Ophrys*: A comprehensive overview of sections, species and hybrid complexes. Verlag Manfred Hennecke, Baden-Württemberg, Germany.
- Turland, N.J., Wiersema, J.H., Barrie, F.R., Gandhi, K.N., Gravendyck, J., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D.L., Herendeen, P.S., Klopper, R.R., Knapp, S., Kusber, W.-H., Li, D.-Z., May, T.W., Monro, A.M., Prado, J., Price, M.J., Smith, G.F. and Zamora Señoret, J.C. (2025). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Madrid Code). Regnum Vegetabile 162. University of Chicago Press, Chicago. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226839479.001.0001>